

Analysis of Near-Far Effect and Multipath Mitigation Techniques for Pseudolite Based Positioning Applications

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Abstract

GPS is the most widely used technology for finding accurate position. However accuracy, availability, and continuity of service for certain high precision applications cannot be met by Global Positioning System (GPS) alone. The GPS like signal transmitted by Pseudolite (PLs) can be employed to augment and provide continuity, accuracy and availability in such environment. The major problems associated with such navigation system are the "Near-Far" and "Multipath problem". Among various methods of mitigating the near-far problem, pulsing of transmitting PL signal for fractions of a full duty cycle and for mitigating multipath effect, adaptive filter such as Least Mean Square (LMS) has been observed to be more effective. In this paper, the degradation of SNR as the user moves away from PL is presented. The effective dynamic range for a typical receiver in case of CW and varying duty cycle signals from a pulsed PL is estimated and graphically presented. Also, the signal degradation with Rayleigh fading channel and multipath error minimization using LMS adaptive filter is presented.

Keywords

Pseudolite, Near-far, Multipath, Signal Pulsing, LMS

I. Introduction

The Global Positioning System (GPS) is a World wide satellite based navigation system developed by the U.S Department of Defense (DOD). The GPS-based positioning services depend on the number of satellites being tracked. But, in some areas like urban canyons and deep open cut mines etc, it is not able to receive signals from sufficient number of satellites for positioning. Hence, Pseudolite or Pseudo-satellites (PLs) which are ground-based transmitters can be employed for providing additional navigation ranging signals. Pseudolite can be installed wherever required; when placed appropriately, they can provide additional signals to users in locations that obscure signals from GPS satellites. Though PLs offer potential benefits, some problems associated with various technical issues such as multipath, Near-Far and time synchronization need to be addressed. Among all these problems, the Near-Far problem and Multipath limits the effective range of truthful positioning. Pulsing the PL signal in the presence of satellite signal has found to be the most competent technique for near-far problem. However, the pulsed PL signals affect GPS receivers depending on its characteristics such as duty cycle and pulse width. In this paper, the impact of pulsed PL signal on the GPS receiver while tracking for satellite signal is presented. Among multipath mitigation techniques, adaptive filter technique using LMS has found to be much effective.

II. Limitations of Pseudolite

To improve the positioning accuracy over a localized limited area on ground, the GPS can be augmented by implementation of ground based PLs [1]. Some of the merits are PL can significantly enhance the satellite geometry, and when used in multiple numbers it can even form a GPS constellation independent navigation system for use over smaller local area [2]. Employing the PL to provide GPS service into the areas which have an obstructed view

of GPS satellites results in continuity as well.

The principle of PL is directly derived from the GPS technology [3].

However, some of its features that differ from GPS are

1. The 50bps data messages of PLs are different.
2. PL uses a low price, relatively less stable TCXO (Temperature Compensated Crystal Oscillator).
3. Ionospheric errors are ignored in PL due to its fixed location near the ground.
4. The PLs expected ranges are much more dynamic due to its power variation with respect to distance.

However, the PL based augmentation system has certain technical issues associated with it such as Time synchronization, Multipath and Near-far problem.

III. Near -Far Effect

A large variation in the range between the pseudolite transmitter and the receiver causes large fluctuations in the received signal power. In the region near the pseudolite, the pseudolite signals can be orders of magnitude stronger than the satellite signal power, making it difficult for the receiver to simultaneously detect the satellite signals. This is called the "Near" problem. If the receiver is moving away from the pseudolite, signal strength or signal power of pseudolite is decreased than satellite signal and occurring a problem is known as "Far" problem receiver range. The average power being received from the GPS Satellite Vehicles (SVs) remains approximately constant due to the large distance of the satellites from users. The PL power varies with the inverse square of the user's distance from the PL, compared to constant power from Satellite Vehicle [4]. As a result, in certain regions called as near region, when the receiver is close to the PL the signals from it cause interference with the GPS satellite signals and may jam the receiver. However, beyond a particular distance away from the PL called as far region, the PL signals will be too weak to be tracked by the GPS receiver as shown in Figure 1. To navigate with signals from both GPS and PL, the receiver must remain in the zone between these two boundaries called as Effective Dynamic Range (EDR), where both sets of signals can be tracked. EDR is defined as the ratio of the strongest and the weakest signals that the receiver can demodulate without excessive noise or distortion.

The near-far problem is required to be addressed for improving the effective dynamic range in PL navigation. Various techniques such as spreading PRN codes, frequency offset, frequency hopping, antenna pattern shaping, signal pulsing and Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) are proposed to overcome the Near-far problem. These approaches can be applied either singly or in combination. However, pulsing the PL signal is quite effective and can virtually eliminate the constraint.

A. Signal Pulsing

The main reason for pulsing is that, a PL signal can interfere with the GPS signal only during the pulses [5]. In this process, the PL signal is broadcasted in short pulses while transmitting nothing in between them. That is, few chips are transmitted at a time and the remaining chips after certain time delay. As a result, the receiver could acquire PL signals from the pulses and satellite

signals in between them.

Ideally, the pulses must be short enough so that the PL signals do not effect the satellite signals. On the other hand, the pulses need to be strong so that PL signals can be easily acquired and tracked. The various parameters to be considered while designing PL pulsing scheme are pulse duration, pulse position and Pulse Duty Cycle (PDC) .

Table 1: ON and OFF Times of a PL Pulse Signal

Duty Cycle	ON Time	OFF Time	SIR Value (dB)
2%	20 μ sec	980 μ sec	15.5
6%	60 μ sec	940 μ sec	11.7
10%	100 μ sec	900 μ sec	9.8
15%	150 μ sec	850 μ sec	8

The pulsing of PL signal can be synchronized or unsynchronized. In synchronized pulsing, a separate broadcast slot is allocated for each PL hence; the risk of interference between the signals can be eliminated. For short time slots multiple numbers of PLs can be used in the same geographic area. In order to provide a unified time reference, an external clock is used. This method needs some extra hardware which yields a higher cost. However, for unsynchronized multiple PLs, the pulses may overlap resulting in pulse interference. This produces a limit on the pulse interference that any given receiver can tolerate, before it begins to lose the track of satellite signals.

Fig. 1: Near-Far Regions

IV. Multipath Effect

Multipath is undesirable for GNSS receivers. It’s mainly caused by reflections of the satellites signal from the ground or from nearby building or other obstacles. Multipath errors result when the receiver receives the direct or line-of-sight (LOS) satellite signal through multiple paths and processes the combined signal as if it were a single path. So these multipath signals have randomly distributed amplitudes and phases and directions of arrival. The various effects due to multipath are signal fading and shadowing effect. Signal fading is the phenomenon of random fluctuations in the received signal level over short time intervals. Shadowing effect is observed as long term variations in the received signal level. A Pseudolite caught in the shadow behind buildings, hills and other large obstacles experience the shadowing effect. Fig. 2 shows the multipath environment.

Fig. 2: Multipath Effect Illustration

A. Multipath Mitigation Methods

There are several approaches to mitigate the multipath propagation such as antenna based methods and signal processing methods.

1. Antenna Based Methods

(i). Sensitivity to RHCP and Axial Ratio

When reflected, the transmitted GNSS signal changes its polarisation into left-hand, unlike a direct signal. The GNSS antenna is designed to have high sensitivity to the right-hand circular polarised signals (RHCP – co-polar signals) and low signals for the left-hand polarised signal (LHCP – cross-polar signals) [6]. A RHCP antenna is small in size, does not need extra signal processing hardware in the receiver, and suppresses the LHCP signals partially, therefore it is not able to mitigate effectively multiple reflected signals. The quality of a Circular Polarised antenna is measured by the ratio of co-polar to cross-polar components recorded by the antenna, identified by means of the Axial Ratio (AR) parameter. A good performance antenna should have an AR parameter close to 1dB in broadside, increasing with decreases in elevation angles, while a high performance antenna should have an AR parameter ranging between 3 to 6 dB with an elevation angle of 10 degrees.

(ii). Choke Ring Ground Plane Antenna

The choke ring ground plane antenna is used to mitigate the low elevation angle reflected signals in the antenna by reducing its gain at low elevation angles and creating a high-impedance surface which prevents propagation of surface waves near the antenna. This method is effective in mitigating low elevation reflected signals, by reducing code and carrier phase multipath errors [7]. The use of a choke ring ground plane antenna has limitations concerning big size and weight, and in dynamic applications where the altitude of the antenna is not fixed causes the elimination of low elevation direct signal when the ground plan is not horizontal.

(iii). Antenna Array

A directional antenna consists of a series of antenna elements combined in an array, in order to be able to have gain in one direction and loss in another direction. An antenna array can distinguish between the multipath signals and the direct one by adding spatial dimension. The combination of applied relative

amplitude and phase shift on each antenna elements is referred to as the complex weight [8]. The correct weight is applied to each element of antenna array by means of signal processing techniques. A directional antenna is big in size and needs additional signal processing techniques.

2. Signal Processing Methods

(i). Narrow Early-Late Correlator

The Narrow early-late correlator method is effective for long delay secondary path and it is not able to track the signal in low Signal to Noise Ratio situations [9].

However, of all these mitigation techniques, adaptive algorithms are most effective.

B. Adaptive Algorithm

Adaptive algorithms have been applied to various problems including noise and echo cancellation, signal prediction, channel equalization, adaptive arrays etc. An adaptive filter can also be used to track the optimum behavior of slowly varying signals due to its real-time self- adjusting characteristic.

It consists of three basic processes:(1). Computing the output of filter in response to an input signal with a filtering process, (2). Generating an estimation error by comparing the output with a desired response 3. Automatic adjustment of filter coefficients (adaptive process) in accordance with the estimation error.

The combination of these three processes working together constitutes a feedback loop, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Block Diagram of Adaptive Transversal Filter

A transversal filter is used for filtering process. The tap weights of this filter are adaptively controlled by an adaptive weight control mechanism. In this paper, a 32 stage adaptive transversal filter consisting of 31 delay elements is considered. Each delay element has its own weight coefficient with which the input sample is multiplied (output of this element). Based on the error signal, the adaptive weight control mechanism calculates the new coefficients, with which the transversal filter weights are multiplied (new weights for the transversal filter). Then the output response of the filter changes with respect to desired signal based on present weights of the filter. This process continues in feedback loop.

V. Results and Discussions

A. Near-far Simulations

Fig. 4 shows the degradation of SNR with respect to the distance

Fig. 4: SNR Versus Distance

Table 2: Comparative analysis of CW and pulsed PL at L1 and L5 frequencies

Signal	Effective range(m) L1(1575.42MHz)	Effective range(m) L5(1176.45MHz)
CW	37083	49642
90%	41169	55125
70%	52932	70875
50%	74265	99185
30%	123608	165475
10%	370825	496425

Table 2 gives the Comparative analysis of CW and pulsed PL for duty cycle greater than 10% at L1 and L5 frequencies. It shows the linear increase of dynamic range with respect to Pulse Duty Cycle (PDC). Hence pulsing has found to be effective.

Fig. 5 to fig. 7 shows the variation of dynamic range for GALILEO and PL based positioning applications.

Fig. 5: GALILEO and Pulsed PL at E1 Frequency

Fig. 6: GALILEO and Pulsed PL at E5a Frequency

Fig. 7: GALILEO and Pulsed PL at E5b Frequency

B. Multipath Simulations

Fig. 8: Comparison of AWGN and Rayleigh Fading Channel

Fig. 8 shows the Fading signal power for the signal taken and it also presents the SNR versus BER of AWGN and Rayleigh fading channels. It has been noticed that Rayleigh has less signal fading characteristics.

Fig. 9: Multipath Mitigation Using LMS Adaptive Filter on L1 Frequency. (a) MP1 (Multipath Error) (b) Desired MP1 (c) Minimized MP1 (d) Filter Convergence Factor

Fig. 9 shows the multipath mitigation using LMS adaptive filter on L1 frequency. It has been observed that by considering Eq (1), multipath error is reduced by 92.5%. The percentage of multipath error reduced by the filter outputs can be estimated as

$$[(Y_i)/X_i]*100, i = 1 \tag{1}$$

Here X_i and Y_i are the mean multipath errors before and after filtering.

VI. Conclusion

The Pulsing of transmitting PL signal has been observed to be most effective for mitigation of near far problem in PL augmented GPS and GALILEO. The effective dynamic range for various duty cycles are calculated and compared with CW PL. Also, Adaptive filter using LMS has been found to be an optimum technique for mitigation of multipath interference. It has been observed that multipath error is reduced by 92.5%.

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